

Electrochemical reduction of *o*-nitrotoluene at glassy carbon and stainless steel electrode at different pH

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Abstract : The voltammogram of *o*-nitrotoluene (aqueous-methanol solution) in BR buffer at different pHs, 4.0, 7.0 and 9.0 exhibits the one reduction peak and effect of scan rate on cathodic peak potential indicates these reactions are irreversible. Constant current electrolysis in acidic and basic media of *o*-nitrotoluene gives *o*-toluidine and 2,2-dimethylazobenzene respectively as a major products which were confirmed by TLC, NMR, IR spectrum analysis.

Keywords : Electrochemical reduction, cyclic voltammetry, constant current electrolysis.

Numerous investigations have been made on the reduction of aromatic nitro compounds under various conditions¹. The synthesis and biological evaluation of aromatic amines are active and important areas of research and their chemistry by derivative formation has been widely studied².

The present work deals with cyclic voltammetry and constant current electrolysis studies at SS-(316) electrode of *o*-nitrotoluene in acidic, neutral and basic media³. Constant current electrolysis at SS cathode *o*-nitrotoluene gave different products in different media, which have been studied in detail by means of various techniques⁴. Economically viable stainless steel electrode (SS-316) has been used successfully in our laboratory⁵.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. The solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Nitrotoluene recrystallized from methanol was used for reduction purpose. Prior to electrolysis, TLC, which gave single spot, was used to check the purity of the compound. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded on a fully computer controlled Basic Electrochemistry System — ECDA 001 (supplied by Conserved Enterprises, Mumbai, India) using 3-electrode cell assembly with 1 mm diameter glassy carbon as working electrode, Ag/AgCl as reference electrode and Pt wire as counter electrode. In aqueous

media, 1.0 mM concentration of depolarizer and KNO₃ was used as supporting electrolyte to maintain the ionic strength of the solution at 0.1 M BR buffer was used to maintain desired pH viz. 4.0, 7.0 and 9.0. Galvanostat, designed and made by CDPE (Centre for Development of Physics Education, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur), was used for carrying out controlled current electrolysis. The solution was stirred throughout the electrolysis. FT-IR spectra of *o*-nitrotoluene and the products were obtained and compared for analysis, identification and characterization. The preparative electrolysis at 200 ml 0.1 M *o*-nitrotoluene was carried out at constant current (at 1 amp) in alkaline solution containing (1 M CH₃COONa + 0.5 M NaOH) as well as in acidic media containing (1 M CH₃COONa + 1 M CH₃COOH, pH = 4) in 1 : 1 CH₃OH : H₂O. After electrolysis the methanol was removed at reduced pressure (30 mm Hg). The catholyte was extracted repeatedly with ether layer. The ether layer was collected in watch glass and was allowed to evaporate. After evaporation the product was recrystallized with absolute alcohol and pure crystals were obtained.

Results and discussion

Most cyclic voltammograms were recorded with an initial potential E_1 of 700 mV and final (switching) potential E_s of -1400 mV at different scan rates viz. 30, 60, 100, 200, 400 and 500 mV/s (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1

A prominent cathodic peak of *o*-nitrotoluene at scan rate of 30 mV/s and pH = 7, 4 and 9 appeared at -896 mV, -644 mV and -866 mV respectively. As the sweep rate was gradually increased to 60, 100, 200, 400 and 500 mV/s peak gradually shifted towards higher values as is expected for an irreversible electron transfer processes.

Table 1 summarizes current potential measurements by cyclic voltammetry for *o*-nitrotoluene in acidic, basic as well as in neutral media, which confirms irreversible nature of the reduction process of *o*-nitrotoluene. Single spot TLC checked the purity of compounds. The identity of products was further confirmed on the basis of melting point and spectroscopic analysis IR and NMR data.

On the basis of all above studies reduction of nitrotoluene (*o*-, *m*- and *p*-) depends on proton availability⁶.

Table 1. Current potential measurement by cyclic voltammetry for *o*-nitrotoluene

Condition applied :

Initial potential E_i : 700 mV

Switching potential E_s : -1400 mV

Electrode applied :

Working electrode : Glassy carbon

Reference electrode : Ag/AgCl

Auxilliary electrode : Platinum

Sl. no.	Medium (pH)	Scan rate (mV/s)	Cathodic wave		Effect of scan rate	Remark (cathodic wave)
			E_{pc} (mV)	I_{pc} (μ A)		
1.	4.0	30	-644	424	With increase scan rate peak potential shifts towards more negative side of potential	Irreversible
2.	4.0	60	-649	486		Irreversible
3.	4.0	100	-651	609		Irreversible
4.	4.0	200	-653	786		Irreversible
5.	4.0	400	-665	1085		Irreversible
6.	4.0	500	-675	1218		Irreversible
7.	7.0	30	-896	511	Peak potential show considerable cathodic shift of potential with increasing scan rates	Irreversible
8.	7.0	60	-909	761		Irreversible
9.	7.0	100	-921	960		Irreversible
10.	7.0	200	-956	1596		Irreversible

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

11.	7.0	400	-962	2321		Irreversible
12.	7.0	500	-965	2609		Irreversible
13.	9.0	30	-866	401	Peak potential shifts towards negative side of potential with increasing scan rates.	Irreversible
14.	9.0	60	-879	575		Irreversible
15.	9.0	100	-887	742		Irreversible
16.	9.0	200	-907	1142		Irreversible
17.	9.0	400	-923	1727		Irreversible
18.	9.0	500	-927	2003		Irreversible

Table 2. Characterization table for synthesis in basic media

Starting material	NMR data (δ)	IR data (cm^{-1})	Product confirmed
<i>o</i> -Nitrotoluene (basic media, m.p. 52.2 °C)	8H, $\delta = 6.7-8.3$ unsymmetrical pattern (aromatic proton), 6H, s, $\delta = 3.3$ (-CH ₃)	1650-1440bs (aromatic ring), 2872s (C-H stretching), 1500-1400w (azo group)	<i>o</i> -Azotoluene (2,2'-dimethyl-azobenzene)
<i>o</i> -Nitrotoluene (acid media b.p. 200 °C)	4H, $\delta = 6.4-7.5$, unsymmetrical pattern (aromatic proton), 3H, s, $\delta = 2.2$ (-CH ₃), 2H, s, $\delta = 4.4$ (-NH ₂)	3030s (Ar-H stretching), 2850s (C-H stretching), 1650-1440bs (aromatic ring), 3400s (symmetric stretching N-H), 3480s (asymmetric stretching N-H), 1620b (bending N-H), 1280s (C-N stretching), 740s (<i>o</i> -substitution)	<i>o</i> -Toluidine (2-methylaniline)

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